

NOTES

Benzyl- β -phenylthiocarbazine (1) on treatment with alkyl/aryl isocyanates in benzene gave the corresponding benzyl β -alkyl/aryl carbamylthiocarbazine (3^a; Table 1). When refluxed in alkaline medium, compound 3 afforded the corresponding 1-phenyl-4-alkyl/aryl-1,2,4-triazolidin-3,5-diones (4; Table 1). One of these, viz. 1,4-diphenyl-1,2,4-triazolidin-3,5-dione (4_a; R=Ph) showed ir band at 1780 and 1710 cm⁻¹ (C=O). Its pmr spectrum (DMSO-d₆) showed peaks at δ 7.0–7.8 (10H, m, ArH) and 5.7 (1H, s, NH).

The antimicrobial activities of compounds 2 and 4 were tested against *B. subtilis* and *E. coli* using plate-diffusion method⁴. Compounds 2 were found to be very active against *E. coli* and moderately active against *B. subtilis*, and 4 were found to be moderately active against *E. coli*.

Experimental

Benzyl- β -phenyl thiocarbazine (1): Through a solution of phenyl hydrazine (0.05 mol) and triethylamine (0.05 mol) in dry methanol (30 ml), a stream of dry carbon oxysulphide was passed for about 20 min and then benzyl chloride (0.05 mol) was added to it. The passing of carbon oxysulphide was continued for 2.5 h. The contents were then poured on crushed ice and triturated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and the resulting solid was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 171°.

1-Phenyl-4-substituted-5-thio-1,2,4-triazolidin-3-ones (2): A mixture of 1 (0.02 mol), alkyl/aryl-isothiocyanate (0.02 mol) and aqueous alcoholic sodium hydroxide (10%; 30 ml) was refluxed for 90 min. The contents were then poured in cold water, acidified with dilute HCl, and the resulting solid was crystallised from alcohol.

Benzyl- β -substituted-carbamyl thiocarbazine (3): A mixture of 1 (0.02 mol) and alkyl/arylisocyanate (0.02 mol) was refluxed in benzene for 30 min. After removing benzene, the resulting solid was crystallised.

1-Phenyl-4-substituted-1,2,4-triazolidin-3,4-diones (4): Compound 3 (0.02 mol) was refluxed in aqueous sodium hydroxide for 30 min. The contents were then poured into crushed ice and the resulting solid was crystallised from alcohol.

Acknowledgement

Authors sincerely thank Dr. V. S. Darshane, Head of the Department of Chemistry for facilities, U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance and Dr. H. P. Tipnis, Principal, Bombay College of Pharmacy, Kalina, for antimicrobial testing facilities.

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Synthesis and Application of some New Quinolinfurandione Derivatives as Bactericides

AMAL S. YANNI* and ZARIF H. KHALIL

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Assiut University, Assiut, Egypt

Manuscript received 16 April 1990, accepted 19 June 1990

SEVERAL heterocyclic quinones possess properties as dyes¹, catalysts² and drugs³, and this led to a renewed attention to their synthesis from 6,7-dichloroquinoline-5,8-quinone.

Results and Discussion

Naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-dione is obtained from 2,3-dichloronaphthoquinone by condensing 2,3-dichloronaphthoquinone with an active methylene group compound in ethanol and in presence of tributylamine⁴. It is therefore expected that 6,7-dichloroquinoline-5,8-quinone can react similarly with active methylene group compounds such as acetylacetone, ethyl acetoacetate, ethyl cyanoacetate, and diethyl malonate to give 6-disubstituted-methyl-7-chloroquinoline-5,8-dione (1), and the cyclisation of 1 in ethanol and in presence of tributylamine

- 1a; R=CH₃, R₁=COCH₃ 2a; R=CH₃, R₁=COCH₃
1b; R=CH₃, R₁=COOC₂H₅ 2b; R=CH₃, R₁=COOC₂H₅
1c; R=OC₂H₅, R₁=CN 2c; R=OC₂H₅, R₁=CN
1d; R=OC₂H₅, R₁COOC₂H₅ 2d; R=OC₂H₅, R₁=COOC₂H₅

yield 2. In another route, compounds 2 could be prepared in one step by condensing 6,7-dichloro-

quinoline-5,8-dione with an active methylene group compound in ethanol and in presence of tributylamine. Very probably the one-step method proceeds via the same intermediate **1**. The compounds contained no halogen and revealed ir bands at 1 050–1 190 (–C–O–C– of cyclic ethers) and 1 655 cm^{-1} (C=O).

The brazanquinones system or benzo[*b*]naphtho [2,3-*d*]furan-6,11-diones, are usually prepared by heating (100°) a mixture of 2,3-dichloroquinone and the phenol in pyridine⁵. Similarly, the products from the reaction of 6,7-dichloroquinoline-5,8-quinone with phenols in presence of pyridine were identified as benzo[*b*]-, and naphtho [1,2- or 2,1-*b*]quinolino[6,7-*d*]furan-6,11-diones (**3**–**6**). In this case pyridine is supposed to act only as a basic reagent facilitating the removal of hydrogen chloride. Compounds **3**–**6** contained no halogen, and the ir spectra revealed bands at 1 050–1 190 (–C–O–C of cyclic ether) and 1 650 cm^{-1} (C=O of quinone) and disappearance of the characteristic bands of $\nu_{\text{C-Cl}}$.

(3)

(3a) R = –H

(3b) R = –OCH₃

(4)

(5)

(6)

The reaction can be represented as

The electronic spectra (ethanol) showed three bands at 230–240, 255–260 and 300–320 nm. They possessed a single broad band at 418–450 nm which can be ascribed to intramolecular charge transfer (C.T.) of electrons on the hetero-oxygen

atom of furan nucleus to the quinone ring. It is also remarkable that C.T. bands of the products obtained from the reaction of quinone and α - or β -naphthol located at 438 and 450 nm respectively, are close to each other with a difference of ~12 nm. This reinforces the postulation that **3** and **4** are linear and not angular and the antagonistic action of naphthyl ring on C.T. does not differ much.

Biological activity: Bactericidal activity was determined by the usual disc assay method against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Protus vulgaris* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Compounds **1**, **2**, **3b**, **5** and **6** showed no remarkable activity against all the organisms. Compound **3a** was active against all, while **4** showed potent activity against *E.c.*, *P.v* and *P.a* and less so against *S.a*.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Unicam SP 1200 spectrophotometer and uv-visible spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 8000 spectrophotometer.

6-Disubstituted-methyl-7-chloroquinoline-5,8-diones (1a–d): 6,7-Dichloroquinoline-5,8-dione (0.005 mol) was added to a boiling solution of the active methylene group compound (0.005 mol) in absolute ethanol containing sodium (0.005 mol), and the mixture was refluxed for ~4 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from aqueous ethanol (Table 1).

TABLE 1 – PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	Colour	M p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1a	Bark brown	120	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄ NCl
1b	Brown red	145	40	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₄ NCl
1c	Violet brown	180	70	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₄ N ₂ Cl
1d	Reddish violet	170	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₄ NCl
2a	Violet brown	215	40	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₄ N
2b	Dark brown	170	25	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₄ N
2c	Brown	195	65	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₄ N ₂
2d	Dark brown	225	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₄ N
3a	Dark brown	310 (sub. 300)	70	C ₁₅ H ₇ O ₃ N
3b	Dark brown	>350	65	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₄ N
4	Violet brown	>350	60	C ₁₅ H ₇ O ₄ N
5	Yellow brown	320	80	C ₁₉ H ₉ O ₄ N
6	Brisk brown	300 dec	75	C ₁₉ H ₉ O ₄ N

*All compounds showed satisfactory elemental analyses for N and/or Cl.

2,3-Disubstituted-quinolinofuran-4,9-diones (2a–d): To a solution of **1** (0.005 mol) in ethanol, tributylamine (0.025 mol) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 8–10 h, then cooled and acidified with acetic acid. The resulting solid was crystallised from methanol (Table 1).

Benzo- or naphthoquinolino[6,7-d]furan-6,11-dione (3-6): A mixture of 6,7-dichloroquinoline-5,8-dione (0.005 mol) and phenol (0.005 mol) was refluxed in pyridine for 8–10 h until the reaction mixture had a permanent colour and yielded a dark solid. The reaction mixture was then cooled and resulting solid was washed with boiling water and crystallised from acetic acid (Table 1).

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Studies on 4-Thiazolidinones. Synthesis and Anti-microbial Activity of 1,4-Bis(2'-aryl-5'(H)-4'-thiazolidinone-3'-ylamino)phthalazine

HASMUKH JOSHI, PARESH UPADHYAY

and

A. J. BAXI*

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University,
Rajkot-360 005

Manuscript received 1 December 1989, revised 20 April 1990,
accepted 19 June 1990

4-THIAZOLIDINONES¹ and phthalazines² possess various biological activities. Dihydralazine is a potent antihypertensive agent³. With a view to obtaining better therapeutic agents we have synthesised different 4-thiazolidinones (3) by the action of thioglycolic acid on Schiff bases obtained by condensing 1,4-dihydrazinophthalazine with different aryl aldehydes (Scheme 1). The structures were supported by ir, mass and pmr spectral studies. The products were screened for anti-microbial activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu IR 435 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on Varian-400 spectrometer.

1,4-Bis(substituted-benzaldehydrazino)phthalazine: A mixture of 1,4-dihydrazinophthalazine (1.9 g,

0.01 mol) and 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (3.32 g, 0.02 mol) dissolved in methanol was refluxed for 15 min on a water-bath. The mixture was then poured into crushed ice and the resulting solid was washed with sodium bisulphite, dried and crystallised from methanol, (54%), m.p. 184° (Found: C, 68.70, N, 17.04. $C_{26}H_{26}N_6O_4$ requires: C, 68.83, N, 17.72%); ν_{max} (KBr) (R=3,4-dimethoxy phenyl) 3 300 (NH), 1 660 (C=N) and 810 cm^{-1} (ring skeletal); δ ($CDCl_3$) (R=3,4-dimethoxy phenyl) 8.6 (2H, s, CH=N), 7.53 (2H, d, CH aromatic), 7.23 (2H, d, CH aromatic), 7.25

Scheme 1